

MENTAL HEALTH LITERACY AND QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the role and status of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) and its relationship with the Quality of Life (QoL) among 327 college students in Negros Occidental during the 2023-2024 academic year. Using a quantitative correlational design, MHL and QoL were measured through the Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS) and the Quality of Life Scale (QOLS). Results showed that students have an average level of MHL, excelling in disorder recognition, risk factors, professional help, and positive mental health promotion. However, areas for improvement include anxiety self-management, digital resource utilization, and reducing stigmatizing beliefs. QoL scores indicated high satisfaction in physical and material well-being, personal development, and recreation, with room for improvement in interpersonal relations and community engagement. Significant differences in MHL and QoL were found based on demographics, with females scoring higher than males, and variations across program clusters reflecting the influence of educational and social environments. A strong positive association between MHL and QoL was identified which highlighted MHL's primary involvement in student well-being. The study recommends that tertiary institutions alike may further enhance MHL through workshops, counseling, and curriculum adjustments to further improve QoL. Future research should investigate causality and include diverse populations to further understand MHL and QoL dynamics.

Keywords: *Mental Health Literacy, MHLS, Quality of Life, QOLS, College Students*

INTRODUCTION

The transition to adulthood is a critical period in a person's life; marked by significant changes and challenges. This is particularly true for college students, who are navigating this transition while also managing the demands of higher education (Serrano & Reyes, 2022). College students are increasingly overwhelmed with responsibilities, leading many to self-diagnose their mental health instead of seeking professional help (Lacsamana, 2022). Also, the use of offensive and derogatory language in discussing mental health and the avoidance of professional help due to stigma and limited awareness are prevalent (Beasley, 2020). Given these circumstances, there is an urgent need to understand and address these challenges to safeguard the well-being of college students.

Mental Health Literacy (MHL), as defined by Jafari et al. (2021), comprises perspectives supporting the identification, treatment, and prevention of mental health issues, including symptom recognition, knowledge of causes, attitudes, and access to services. Quality of Life (QoL), according to the World Health Organization (2012, as cited in Jafari, 2021), pertains to an individual's understanding of their life position in relation to subjective, standards, expectations, and cultural values.

Reports from global studies include students' demonstration of lower MHL compared to most studies in the literature. Undergraduate students were less knowledgeable about environmental, social, familial, or biological factors that increase the risk of developing a mental illness (Chinene et al., 2023). Conversely, this is similar to the results of Arslan and Karabey (2023) which showed us that MHL levels are low in high schools. Another study examined levels of MHL among university students and assessed that there is a relationship between MHL and help-seeking behaviors (Moss et al., 2022). In most studies, the QoL is associated with the broader spectrum of General Health Literacy (GHL). Students in China who were equipped with GHL were associated with greater QoL (Ran et al., 2018). This verifies the study of Ishikawa et al. (2021) which suggested that the decline in GHL may be important for attenuating the decline in QoL.

Finally, the research gap was evident as there was a lack of studies exploring the direct relationship between MHL and QoL among college students. Previous research has primarily focused on general health knowledge, identifying an area for further investigation on how MHL specifically impacts students' QoL. Furthermore, while there has been considerable research about how MHL affects help-seeking behavior, there was a notable gap about how it directly influences students' overall Quality of Life. Moreover, there was a shortage of baseline data on MHL and QoL levels within the context of the institution, impeding the development of effective strategies to support students' mental health. This research aimed to focus on Mental Health Literacy and its potential association with the Quality of Life among students. By improving our understanding of these issues, we can develop more effective strategies to support students during this critical period of their lives.

Research Questions

This study aimed to investigate the role and status of MHL and its association with their QoL among college students during the academic year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to address the following research questions:

1. What is the level of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) of the participants when assessed in terms of the following subscales and when taken as a whole:
 - 1.1. Disorder Recognition
 - 1.2. Risk-Factor Knowledge
 - 1.3. Self-Treatment Knowledge
 - 1.4. Available Professional Help Knowledge
 - 1.5. Information Seeking Knowledge
 - 1.6. Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion
2. What is the level of Quality of Life (QoL) of the participants when assessed in terms of the following subscales and when taken as a whole:
 - 2.1. Physical and Material Well-Being
 - 2.2. Relations with Other People
 - 2.3. Social, Community, and Civic Activities
 - 2.4. Personal Development and Fulfillment
 - 2.5. Recreation
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) of the participants when grouped according to their demographic profile, specifically:
 - 3.1. Sex
 - 3.2. Program Cluster
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of Quality of Life (QoL) of the participants when grouped according to their demographic profile, specifically:
 - 4.1. Sex
 - 4.2. Program Cluster
5. Is there a significant association between the level of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) and the Quality of Life (QoL) of the participants?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative correlational research design to examine the potential association between Mental Health Literacy (MHL) and Quality of Life (QoL) among college students. This data-driven approach relied on numerical measures and statistical analysis to explore relationships between variables, as collected through questionnaires and surveys (Fleetwood, 2023). This observational method allowed for the analysis of potential connections between the variables, though it could not definitively establish causal relationships (Cherry, 2023). Consequently, the quantitative, non-experimental correlational design was well-suited to the study's objectives, which facilitated an exploration of potential linkages between MHL and QoL. The findings offer

valuable insights and establish a foundation for future research that may seek to determine causality through experimental designs.

Participants of the Study

The study focused on 327 students from a private Catholic institution in Negros Occidental, representing 15% of the total population of 2,179 students enrolled in various courses in the College Department. A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure a representative sample across different academic program clusters, namely the College of Business and Accountancy (CBA), College of Education (COED), College of Arts and Sciences (CAS), and College of Criminal Justice (CCJ). The sample consisted of 200 female and 127 male students, ensuring balanced gender representation. CBA had the largest group with 133 students, followed by COED with 109, CCJ with 60, and CAS with 25. This diverse distribution of participants allowed for a comprehensive examination of the research variables across different demographics, which facilitated more targeted interpretations and practical implications regarding their levels of Mental Health Literacy and Quality of Life.

Research Instruments

The Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS), developed by O'Connor and Leanne Casey in 2015, was designed to measure mental health literacy across six attributes using 35 items. These attributes included Disorder Recognition, Risk-Factor Knowledge, Self-Treatment Knowledge, Available Professional Help Knowledge, Information Seeking Knowledge, and Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion. Each attribute contained specific items, scored on a Likert scale ranging from 4 to 5 points, assessing participants' awareness and understanding of mental health disorders, treatment options, and available resources. The MHLS was adapted to fit the Philippine context by revising some items to reflect current mental health terminology and culturally relevant questions. It has been widely used in diverse populations, including students, and has shown strong reliability and validity, with Cronbach's alpha averaging 0.818 globally (El Khalil, 2023) and 0.78 among Filipino college students (Batiandila et al., 2023), which indicates high internal consistency. Test-retest reliability also showed consistency over time, with an intraclass correlation coefficient of 0.869 (Montagni & Caballero, 2022), while content and construct validity confirmed its robustness as a tool for measuring MHL (Korhonen et al., 2022; Nejatian et al., 2021).

The Quality of Life Scale (QOLS), originally created by John Flanagan in the 1970s and later expanded by Carol Burckhardt in 2003, was used to evaluate participants' satisfaction across five dimensions: Physical and Material Well-Being, Relations with Other People, Social, Community, and Civic Activities, Personal Development and Fulfillment, and Recreation. The 16-item version, rated on a 7-point Likert scale from "terrible" to "delighted," provided a comprehensive assessment of QoL, which captured participants' subjective experiences in these key areas. The QOLS demonstrated excellent psychometric properties, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87, which indicates strong internal consistency, and test-retest reliability scores ranging from 0.78 to 0.92 (Burckhardt et al., 2003, as cited in Flaherty, 2022). Construct validity was supported by

negative correlations with mental health measures such as the Center for Epidemiologic Studies-Depression and the Davidson Trauma Scale, further confirming the scale's effectiveness in evaluating overall QoL (Jaradat et al., 2022).

Data Gathering Procedures

To ensure rigor and ethical compliance, the researchers adhered to the following comprehensive data-gathering procedures:

Before the conduct of the study, formal approval letters were obtained from the respective Deans' offices of all program clusters involved in the study. Approved questionnaires were then reproduced in sufficient quantities for distribution. An informed consent form was created and presented to potential participants, which outlined the study's purpose, procedures, risks and benefits, and participants' rights.

In addition, during designated classroom visits, researchers utilized vacant periods to minimize class disruption while administering the paper-pencil survey instruments. Participants were then briefed on the study's significance, eligibility criteria, and confidentiality assurances, with particular emphasis on the voluntary and anonymous nature of participation. To ensure accurate responses, researchers clarified terms and addressed any questions. Researchers implemented data quality control measures during data collection, such as checking for incomplete responses, inconsistencies, or outliers.

Finally, after the conduct of the study, a secure data storage and management plan was implemented to protect the confidentiality of participant data. Afterward, collected data was tabulated and analyzed with the assistance of a statistician to determine appropriate statistical tools and generate conclusions and recommendations for the study.

Data Analysis

Statistical tools were applied to analyze the data and address the research questions. To determine the level of MHL and QoL among participants, the mean was utilized. The mean provided the average score for the participants when assessed in terms of subscales and as a whole. For the Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS), scores ranging from 35 to 76 were classified as indicating Low MHL, scores between 77 and 118 reflected Average MHL, and scores from 119 to 160 represented High MHL, following Publico's (2021) method. Similarly, for the Quality of Life Scale (QOLS), scores from 16 to 48 were interpreted as Low QoL, scores between 49 and 80 signified Average QoL, and scores ranging from 81 to 112 indicated High QoL, based on Sharma and Kaur's (2012) approach.

To determine significant differences in MHL and QoL based on demographic factors, a t-test for independent samples was used for data grouped by sex, and a one-way ANOVA was used for the program cluster. These tests helped evaluate whether there were statistically significant differences between the groups. Additionally, Pearson

correlation was employed to assess the relationship between participants' MHL and QoL, determining the strength and direction of the association between these two continuous variables. All statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS, which ensured that the MHL and QOLS scores were accurately calculated and interpreted in line with established research practices.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1 *Level of MHL among college students in terms of Disorder Recognition*

Indicators	Mean	SD
1. If someone became extremely nervous or anxious in one or more situations with other people or performance situations in which they were afraid of being evaluated by others and that they would act in a way that was humiliating or feel embarrassed, then to what extent do you think it is likely they have Social Phobia?	2.93	.76
2. If someone experienced excessive worry about a number of events or activities where this level of concern was not warranted, had difficulty controlling this worry and had physical symptoms such as having tense muscles and feeling fatigued then to what extent do you think it is likely they have Generalized Anxiety Disorder?	2.83	.71
3. If someone experienced a low mood for two or more weeks, had a loss of pleasure or interest in their normal activities and experienced changes in their appetite and sleep then to what extent do you think it is likely they have Major Depressive Disorder?	2.85	.84
4. To what extent do you think it is likely that Personality Disorders are a category of mental illness?	2.84	.84
5. To what extent do you think it is likely that Persistent Depressive Disorder is a disorder?	2.80	.80
6. To what extent do you think it is likely that the diagnosis of Agoraphobia includes anxiety about situations where escape may be difficult or embarrassing?	2.80	.72
7. To what extent do you think it is likely that the diagnosis of Bipolar Disorder includes experiencing periods of elevated (i.e., high) and periods of depressed (i.e., low) mood?	2.82	.83
8. To what extent do you think it is likely that the diagnosis of Substance Abuse Disorder includes physical and psychological tolerance of the drug?	2.85	.94
Overall	22.73	(Hi 4.19)

Legend: 1-8 (Low), 9-16 (Moderate), 17-24 (High), 25-32 (Very High)

Table 1.1 showed a high level of Mental Health Literacy in the Disorder Recognition domain among college students, with an overall mean of 22.73. This indicated a substantial capacity to accurately recognize symptoms of various mental health disorders, which was crucial for early identification and seeking appropriate help.

This suggested that college students were more likely to understand when they or others needed professional support. These findings reflected those of Abesinghe et al. (2023), showing that while most could recognize disorders like depression and schizophrenia, recognition was lower for dementia and social phobia. Moreover, data from a previously conducted investigation done by Cormier et al. (2022) further supported the results, as it revealed that the majority of college students could identify mental illness in various scenarios, indicating knowledge of disorders such as schizophrenia, depression, and social anxiety. Tohme et al. (2024) suggested that familiarity with mental disorders and the ability to recognize them, influenced by personal experiences, curiosity, and emotional presence for others, can reduce stigma and increase awareness of symptoms and treatments.

Table 1.2 *Level of MHL among college students in terms of Risk-Factor Knowledge*

Indicators	Mean	SD
9. To what extent do you think it is likely that in general in Philippines, women are MORE likely to experience a mental illness of any kind compared to men	2.94	.88
10. To what extent do you think it is likely that in general, in Philippines, men are MORE likely to experience an anxiety disorder compared to women	2.38	.80
Overall	5.31 (High)	1.14

Legend: 1-2 (Low), 3-4 (Moderate), 5-6 (High), 7-8 (Very High)

Table 1.2 revealed a high level of MHL in the Risk-Factor Knowledge domain among college students, with an overall mean of 5.31. This indicated their broad awareness of biological, familial, societal, and environmental factors contributing to mental health issues, particularly regarding gender and social determinants. Renwick et al. (2022) supported this, noting adolescents' growing attribution of mental illness to social factors like gender and stressful life events, suggesting a generational shift towards a biopsychosocial understanding, reflecting a shift toward a biopsychosocial perspective. Conversely, Puspitasari et al. (2020) found that most students lacked specific knowledge about risk factors and treatments, potentially due to variations in formal education on mental health. Publico (2020) further asserted that the technical nature of medical jargon in this domain might hinder some students' understanding.

Table 1.3 *Level of MHL among college students in terms of Self-Treatment Knowledge*

Indicators	Mean	SD
11. To what extent do you think it would be helpful for someone to improve their quality of sleep if they were having difficulties managing their emotions (e.g., becoming very anxious or depressed)	3.03	.87
12. To what extent do you think it would be helpful for someone	2.03	.83

to avoid all activities or situations that made them feel anxious if they were having difficulties managing their emotions

Overall **5.06 (High)** **.95**

Legend: 1-2 (Low), 3-4 (Moderate), 5-6 (High), 7-8 (Very High)

Table 1.3 presented the level of MHL in terms of Self-Treatment Knowledge, with an overall mean of 5.06, indicating a high literacy level. This result reflected students' substantial awareness of self-treatment strategies recommended by mental health professionals, which highlighted their ability to manage mental health independently and effectively. These findings contrasted with studies showing gaps in this area. Chen et al. (2022) reported low self-care abilities among individuals with severe disorders, particularly in social and household functioning. Jonsson et al. (2023) found that 60% of Swedish physicians engaged in self-prescribing psychotropic medications, revealing deficiencies in self-treatment knowledge even among healthcare professionals. Anjorin and Wada (2022) noted a public preference for traditional healers over biomedical approaches. Similarly, Patterson (2023) identified limitations in both biomedical and spiritual approaches, which led patients to seek spiritual help despite its own shortcomings.

Table 1.4 *Level of MHL among college students in terms of Available Professional Help Knowledge*

Indicators	Mean	SD
13. To what extent do you think it is likely that Cognitive Behavior Therapy (CBT) is a therapy based on challenging negative thoughts and increasing helpful behaviors	3.00	.74
14. Mental health professionals are bound by confidentiality; however, there are certain conditions under which this does not apply. To what extent do you think it is likely that the following is a condition that would allow a mental health professional to break confidentiality: If you are at immediate risk of harm to yourself or others	2.82	.74
15. Mental health professionals are bound by confidentiality; however, there are certain conditions under which this does not apply. To what extent do you think it is likely that the following is a condition that would allow a mental health professional to break confidentiality: If your problem is not life-threatening and they want to assist others to better support you	2.15	.83
Overall	7.97 (High)	1.24

Legend: 1-3 (Low), 4-6 (Moderate), 7-9 (High), 10-12 (Very High)

The mean score of 7.97 in Table 1.4 confirmed that students were highly literate in the area of Available Professional Help Knowledge, reflecting students' substantial awareness of available professional help and mental health services, including therapeutic approaches and ethical considerations like confidentiality. This awareness

was vital in enabling students to make informed decisions about seeking assistance from mental health professionals, potentially improving mental health outcomes. These findings aligned with Yasri (2017) as cited in Salsabilla et al. (2023), who found that trust in confidentiality significantly influenced students' willingness to engage in counseling services, while lack of trust deterred help-seeking. Similarly, Martinez et al. (2020) identified gaps in the utilization of mental health services among Filipinos, citing stigma and limited awareness as barriers, which emphasized the need for greater education on accessing professional resources. Moreover, Berg et al. (2020) highlighted adolescents' varying levels of knowledge and application of CBT, suggesting the importance of personalized education and skills training for effective self-management. Ponzini et al. (2021) also emphasized improving CBT education, particularly for women, who showed limited awareness of its principles.

Table 1.5 *Level of MHL among college students in terms of Information-Seeking Knowledge*

Indicators	Mean	SD
16. I am confident that I know where to seek information about mental illness	3.74	.92
17. I am confident using the computer or telephone to seek information about mental illness	3.69	.88
18. I am confident attending face to face appointments to seek information about mental illness (e.g., seeing the GP)	3.82	.97
19. I am confident I have access to resources (e.g., GP, internet, friends) that I can use to seek information about mental illness	3.80	.90
Overall	15.05 (High)	2.84

Legend: 1-5 (Low), 6-10 (Moderate), 11-15 (High), 16-20 (Very High)

Table 1.5 showed a high level of MHL in the Information-Seeking Knowledge domain among college students, with an overall mean score of 15.05. This indicated that students were confident and skilled in seeking information on mental health, actively utilizing diverse resources to address their concerns. Such literacy was critical for managing mental health effectively, enabling access to necessary support and services. These findings aligned with Abrams (2022), who observed that students' demand for face-to-face appointments stemmed from prior mental health treatment experience, reflecting growing societal acceptance. However, Mahmoodi et al. (2022) noted low confidence in using digital tools, which emphasized the need for improved e-health literacy due to risks of inaccurate information online. Stunden et al. (2020) identified information overload as a barrier, highlighting the value of reliable and user-friendly platforms. Similarly, Lee et al. (2023) highlighted that familiarity and media exposure influenced mental health knowledge and attitudes.

Table 1.6

Level of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) among college students in terms of Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion

Indicators	Mean	SD
20. People with a mental illness could snap out of it if they wanted	2.76	1.01
21. A mental illness is a sign of personal weakness	2.72	1.17
22. A mental illness is not a real medical illness	3.52	1.15
23. People with a mental illness are dangerous	3.19	1.10
24. It is best to avoid people with a mental illness so that you don't develop this problem	3.58	1.14
25. If I had a mental illness, I would not tell anyone	3.68	1.17
26. Seeing a mental health professional means you are not strong enough to manage your own difficulties	3.45	1.20
27. If I had a mental illness, I would not seek help from a mental health professional	3.65	1.20
28. I believe treatment for a mental illness, provided by a mental health professional, would not be effective	3.58	1.26
29. How willing would you be to move next door to someone with a mental illness?	3.53	.91
30. How willing would you be to spend an evening socializing with someone with a mental illness?	3.61	.84
31. How willing would you be to make friends with someone with a mental illness?	3.79	.89
32. How willing would you be to have someone with a mental illness start working closely with you on a job?	3.45	.88
33. How willing would you be to have someone with a mental illness marry into your family?	3.16	.94
34. How willing would you be to vote for a politician if you knew they had suffered a mental illness?	2.87	.99
35. How willing would you be to employ someone if you knew they had a mental illness?	3.15	1.01
Overall	53.68 (High)	7.60

Legend: 16-32 (Low), 33-48 (Moderate), 49-64 (High), 65-80 (Very High)

Table 1.6 demonstrated a high level of MHL among college students regarding Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion, with an overall mean score of 53.68. The findings indicated that students generally held a favorable outlook towards mental health promotion, sought professional assistance, and maintained positive attitudes towards individuals with mental disorders, rejecting stigmatizing beliefs. This reflected an informed and empathetic stance, suggesting students' awareness could facilitate early intervention, reduce stigma, and promote a supportive community. However, lower mean scores highlighted lingering hesitations in accepting mental illness in specific social contexts. These are the areas where further education and attitude shifts are needed. These findings aligned with Puspitasari et al. (2020), who reported that

students exhibited optimism and a general understanding of mental health conditions. Similarly, Alqassim et al. (2022) observed positive attitudes towards individuals with mental illness but noted persistent negative views, such as opposition to marriage or parenthood for those with mental disorders, revealing gaps in knowledge. Johnson et al. (2023) further supported these results, showing that students were willing to seek help early and make personal adjustments to enhance their well-being.

Table 1.7

Level of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) among college students as a whole

Dimensions	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Disorder Recognition	22.73	4.19	High
Risk-Factor Knowledge	5.31	1.14	High
Self -Treatment Knowledge	5.06	.95	High
Available Professional Help Knowledge	7.97	1.24	High
Information Seeking Knowledge	15.05	2.84	High
Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion	53.68	7.60	High
Overall	109.80	10.62	Average MHL

Legend for the Overall: 35-76 (Low MHL), 77-118 (Average MHL), 119-160 (High MHL)

As shown in Table 1.7, college students exhibited an average level of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) with an overall mean score of 109.80 and a standard deviation of 10.62. While the MHL dimensions demonstrated a high level of literacy, this fell short of achieving a high literacy rating for MHL, as per Publico (2020), who categorized scores in the range of 77-118 as Average MHL. This outcome indicated that students had adequate knowledge and skills to address mental health challenges, contributing to a more informed and proactive college community. This positive trend suggests that students are equipped to seek help, support each other, and engage in mental health promotion. Comparing these results with previous studies, the average MHL score in this study was relatively lower than those reported by Argao et al. (2021), who found a score of 118.15 among Filipino college students, and Gorczynski and Sims-Schouten (2024), who reported a mean of 123.96 among US university students. These results were also lower than those of O'Connor & Casey (2015), White & Casey (2017), and Sullivan et al. (2019), who reported higher MHL scores (ranging from 127.4 to 145.5) for university students, community samples, and healthcare professionals. Additionally, the COVID-19 era has contributed to reduced stigma and increased awareness of mental health, as noted by Tohme et al. (2024), which may have influenced the favorable attitudes and knowledge towards mental health observed in this study, particularly in remote areas of the Philippines where stigma persists (Publico, 2020).

Table 2.1 Level of QOL among college students in terms of Physical and Material Well-Being

Indicators	Mean	SD
1. Material comforts home, food, conveniences, financial security	5.35	1.19
2. Health – being physically fit and vigorous	5.32	1.27
16. Independence, doing for yourself	5.49	1.25
Overall	18.02 (Very High)	11.78

Legend: 3-7 (Low), 8-12 (Moderate), 13-17 (High), 18-21 (Very High)

In Table 2.1, college students showed a high level of satisfaction in the Physical and Material Well-Being domain, with an overall mean of 18.02. This suggested that students felt balanced in their material comforts, financial security, physical health, and independence, contributing to their sense of security and autonomy. However, Sulaiman et al. (2020) pointed out that financial instability is linked to food insecurity, challenging the idea of students' complete satisfaction with their material comforts. On the other hand, Yarmohammadi et al. (2020) found that most students had moderate to high body satisfaction, while Castellanos-Silva & Steins (2023) noted that unrealistic beauty standards on social media could affect body image and mental health. Despite these concerns, the high mean result was in line with Palimaru et al. (2023) and Gharebaglou et al. (2021), who emphasized the importance of stable housing and access to resources in fostering a sense of safety, ease, and independence, ultimately contributing to overall well-being.

Table 2.2 Level of QoL among college students in terms of Relations with other People

Indicators	Mean	SD
3. Relationships with parents, siblings & other relatives – communicating, visiting, helping	5.51	1.24
4. Having and rearing children	4.73	1.33
5. Close relationships with spouse or significant other	5.10	1.27
6. Close friends	5.48	1.19
Overall	20.80 (High)	3.44

Legend: 4-10 (Low), 11-16 (Moderate), 17-22 (High), 23-28 (Very High)

Table 2.2 revealed a high level of satisfaction concerning Relationships with other People with an overall mean score of 20.80. This suggested that strong social connections and supportive networks greatly contributed to their emotional security, sense of belonging, and overall well-being. Aloia (2020) highlighted that open communication within families enhances parent-child relationships during emerging adulthood, while Martínez-Royert et al. (2022) found that good family dynamics lead to higher life satisfaction. Similarly, Zuo et al. (2022) noted that strong parental support, especially from mothers and fathers, exhibit higher life satisfaction. In contrast, Höglund and Hildingsson (2023) noted that some individuals opt for a child-free lifestyle to prioritize

freedom, independence, and self-determination, consistent with the lower emphasis on having children among students in this study.

Table 2.3 *Level of QoL among college students in terms of Social, Community, and Civic Activities*

Indicators	Mean	SD
7. Helping and encouraging others, volunteering, giving advice	5.45	1.22
8. Participating in organizations and public affairs	5.11	1.34
Overall	10.55 (High)	2.21

Legend: 2-5 (Low), 6-8 (Moderate), 9-11 (High), 12-14 (Very High)

In Table 2.3, college students demonstrated a high level of satisfaction, with an overall mean of 10.55 in the Social, Community, and Civic Activities domain. This suggested active participation in diverse activities beyond their immediate social circles, which foster a strong sense of belonging and civic responsibility. Lee (2023) supported these findings, emphasizing the importance of social and civic engagement, like volunteering, as part of loneliness therapies. Dickinson et al. (2021) highlighted that while students valued extracurricular activities for social, civic, or career benefits, barriers such as finances and time often limited their involvement. Moreover, Dolipas (2021) noted that low political engagement among students, shaped by negative perceptions and media influence, called for research-based education and civic activities to cultivate informed and engaged citizens.

Table 2.4 *Level of QoL among college students in terms of Personal Development And Fulfillment*

Indicators	Mean	SD
9. Learning – attending school, improving understanding, getting additional knowledge	5.63	1.16
10. Understanding yourself – knowing your assets and limitations – knowing what life is about	5.58	1.21
11. Work – job or in home	5.28	1.27
12. Expressing yourself creatively	5.62	1.18
Overall	22.12 (High)	3.75

Legend: 4-10 (Low), 11-16 (Moderate), 17-22 (High), 23-28 (Very High)

In Table 2.4, the overall mean score of 22.12 highlighted a high QoL among college students, reflecting strong satisfaction in their personal growth and fulfillment. This suggested that students were deeply engaged in learning, experiencing self-discovery, and aligning their efforts with life goals. Gopal et al. (2021) emphasized that instructors' quality significantly impacts student satisfaction in learning, which highlights the importance of effective course delivery and understanding of student psychology. Moreover, Barroso and Dias (2023) emphasized the impact of a creative and stimulating

classroom environment on fostering student engagement. Prifti (2022) further connected learning with personal development, noting how self-understanding and creative expression contributed to student satisfaction.

Table 2.5 *Level of QoL among college students in terms of Recreation*

Indicators	Mean	SD
13. Socializing – meeting other people, doing things, parties, etc.	5.40	1.32
14. Reading, listening to music, or observing entertainment	5.78	1.14
15. Participating in active recreation	5.46	1.19
Overall	16.66 (High)	2.88

Legend: 3-7 (*Low*), 8-12 (*Moderate*), 13-17 (*High*), 18-21 (*Very High*)

Table 2.5 revealed a high overall mean of 16.66 for the quality of life (QoL) among college students, which reflects their satisfaction with recreational activities. This suggested that students actively engaged in meaningful social interactions and recreational pursuits, contributing to their relaxation, enjoyment, and overall well-being. Nature is fundamental in enhancing student’s well-being by promoting physical activity, reducing stress, strengthening social bonds, and fostering self-reflection and awareness (Puhakka, 2021). Reflecting on adventurous experiences further boosted resilience, self-efficacy, and personal empowerment (Alvestad & Johansen, 2020). Moreover, outdoor adventure education programs were shown to enhance personal growth and social connections, as valued by faculty (Down et al., 2023). Thus, providing customized programs and support for the participants was emphasized as essential to maximize the benefits of outdoor recreation (Lieberman et al., 2022).

Table 2.6 *Level of Quality of Life (QoL) among college students as a whole*

Dimensions	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Physical and Material Well-Being	18.02	11.78	Very High
Relations with other People	20.80	3.44	High
Social, Community, and Civic Activities	10.55	2.21	High
Personal Development and Fulfillment	22.12	3.75	High
Recreation	16.66	2.88	High
Overall	86.29	11.94	High QoL

Legend for the Overall: 16-48 (*Low QoL*), 49-80 (*Average QoL*), 81-112 (*High QoL*)

In Table 2.6, the overall mean QoL score among college students was 86.29, with a standard deviation of 11.94, which aligns with the 81-112 range denoting a high level of QoL. This result suggests that college students experienced a generally satisfying and holistic QoL, likely influenced by factors within the college environment. While this score reflects a positive outcome, it is slightly below the average QoL score of 90 reported for healthy populations in Burckhardt et al.'s (2003) study. Nevertheless, the result is marginally higher than the mean QoL scores of 78.96 and 82.38 observed among Filipino

graduating students (Orines et al., 2023) and Pakistani undergraduates (Ameer et al., 2022), respectively, which highlights potential variations across cultural and educational settings. This disparity is consistent with prior research suggesting that QoL outcomes are shaped by socio-economic and psychological factors. Li and Zhong (2022) noted that students often experience poorer QoL due to mental health challenges influenced by low family income, childhood adversities, and academic stress. Addressing these issues requires universities to enhance support systems through mentoring and counseling, as Cheah et al. (2021) advocated, while also equipping students with effective strategies to manage stress, anxiety, and depression. These efforts are essential for fostering a supportive environment that promotes students' overall well-being and development.

Table 3.1 *Difference Analysis on the level of MHL of the participants when grouped according to Sex*

Dimensions	Mean	t	p	Interpretation
Disorder Recognition	M=22.03; F=23.17	-2.410	.016	Sig.
Risk-Factor Knowledge	M=5.02; F=5.51	-3.877	.000	Highly Sig.
Self -Treatment Knowledge	M=5.17; F=5.00	1.577	.116	Not Sig.
Available Professional Help Knowledge	M=7.83; F=8.06	-1.592	.113	Not Sig.
Information Seeking Knowledge	M=14.68; F=15.29	-1.892	.059	Not Sig.
Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion	M=52.39; F=54.50	-2.456	.015	Sig.
Overall	M=107.11; F=111.51	-3.723	.000	Highly Sig.

M-Male, F-Female; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 3.1 presents an overview of the MHL dimensions, which focuses on sex-based variations. The results revealed that, overall, females had a significantly higher MHL score ($\mu = 111.51$) compared to males ($\mu = 107.11$), with a t-value of -3.723 and a p-value of .000. This significant difference suggests that female students tend to possess a higher level of MHL than their male counterparts. Furthermore, while some dimensions yield results that show notable differences, others do not reach significance levels, which indicates that not all dimensions exhibit significant sex-based discrepancies in MHL.

The study's findings align with previous research, such as Wu et al. (2020), which noted that females and medical students generally exhibit healthier coping mechanisms, possibly linked to a higher psychological resilience style. Furthermore, research by Hadjimina and Furnham (2017), cited in Adu et al. (2023), suggested that women are more likely than men to recognize mental disorders. On the other hand, Staiger et al. (2020) found that men often avoid seeking help due to internalized norms, yet opinions on depression changed after using mental health services. Even so, the overall discrepancies in the level of MHL among college students are aligned with the results from Gorczynski & Sims-Schouten (2024), which revealed that compared to men (μ

= 116.64), women ($\mu = 128.84$) scored significantly higher, suggesting that women are considerably more knowledgeable in mental health than males. This emphasizes the need to address the educational gaps, particularly for male students, to ensure equal opportunities for both genders to improve their mental health knowledge.

Table 3.2 *Difference Analysis on the level of MHL of the participants when grouped according to the Program Cluster*

Dimensions	Mean	F	p	Interpretation
Disorder Recognition	A=23.00; C=23.40 B=23.04; D=21.27	3.096	.027	Sig.
Risk-Factor Knowledge	A=5.45; C=5.24 B=5.14; D=5.48	2.023	.111	Not Sig.
Self -Treatment Knowledge	A=4.99; C=5.16 B=5.13; D=5.00	.583	.626	Not Sig.
Available Professional Help Knowledge	A=7.93; C=9.04 B=7.93; D=7.68	7.814	.000	Highly Sig.
Information Seeking Knowledge	A=14.97; C=16.16 B=15.20; D=14.40	2.492	.060	Not Sig.
Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion	A=55.97; C=58.52 B=52.41; D=50.30	13.216	.000	Highly Sig.
Overall	A=112.31; C=117.52 B=108.85; D=104.13	13.981	.000	Highly Sig.

A=COED, B=CBA, C=CAS, D=CCJ; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 3.2 presented the dimensions of MHL and their discrepancies across program clusters. The CAS consistently scored the highest across MHL measures, with a total mean score of 117.52, while the CCJ recorded the lowest at 104.13. The ANOVA analysis revealed a significant difference among clusters, with an F-value of 13.981 and a p-value of .000, which indicate statistical significance. Notable disparities emerged in specific dimensions, such as Disorder Recognition and Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion, further supporting the rejection of the null hypothesis and suggesting varying levels of MHL based on students' academic programs. These results implied that factors like access to mental health education and promotion might influence the differences observed.

The findings aligned with prior studies, including Nguyen et al. (2021), who identified significant disparities in MHL among Vietnamese university students across different academic disciplines, particularly among sociology and public health students. Similarly, Hương and Minh (2017), as cited in Nguyen et al. (2021), noted challenges in correctly defining mental health terms among third-year students in various fields. Koutra (2024) reinforced the role of discipline-specific factors, finding that psychology students exhibited more positive attitudes and lower self-stigma towards seeking help compared to other social science students. Baklola et al. (2024) further supported these findings, highlighting medical students' superior performance in Disorder Recognition and more

positive mental health attitudes compared to non-medical peers. Overall, the results support the notion of significant variations in MHL across program clusters, which emphasize the importance of understanding disciplinary differences across program clusters.

Table 4.1 *Difference Analysis on the level of QoL of the participants when grouped according to Sex*

Dimensions	Mean	t	p	Interpretation
Physical and Material Well-Being	M=15.66; F=19.51	-3.578	.000	Highly Sig.
Relations with other People	M=20.24; F=21.16	-2.362	.019	Sig.
Social, Community, and Civic Activities	M=10.01; F=10.90	-3.618	.000	Highly Sig.
Personal Development and Fulfillment	M=21.35; F=22.61	-3.004	.003	Highly Sig.
Recreation	M=16.06; F=17.04	-3.023	.003	Highly Sig.
Overall	M=83.32; F=88.18	-3.648	.000	Highly Sig.

M-Male, F-Female; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 4.1 showed significant differences in QoL dimensions when grouped by sex. Females consistently reported higher scores across multiple domains, with an overall mean QoL score of 88.18 compared to males' 83.32. The t-value of -3.64 and p-value of .000 confirmed a highly significant difference. This suggests discernible variations in the level of QoL experienced by males and females which highlight sex as an important determinant in shaping perceptions of and satisfaction with life.

These results aligned with previous studies, such as Mridha (2020), which indicated that females experienced a greater sense of fulfillment regarding their living space and material comforts. Similarly, Xi et al. (2022) found that females tended to engage more in altruistic behaviors, which contributed to a stronger sense of purpose in life. However, the overall pattern among college students differed from Lee et al. (2020) and Louzado et al. (2021), who reported higher global QoL levels among males, attributing this to factors like sociodemographics, clinical conditions, and societal roles. Women's higher perception of health conditions was linked to caregiving roles, while men's scores were often influenced by patriarchal views, which reflect complex gender-based disparities in QoL. Regardless, the findings reinforce the nature of gender-specific disparities in various dimensions of QoL.

Table 4.2 *Difference Analysis on the level of QoL of the participants when grouped according to the Program Cluster*

Dimensions	Mean	F	p	Interpretation
Physical and Material Well-Being	A=16.45; C=17.56 B=20.75; D=14.98	4.513	.004	Highly Sig.

Relations with other People	A=21.15; C=22.32 B=20.81; D=19.53	4.874	.002	Highly Sig.
Social, Community, and Civic Activities	A=10.79; C=11.76 B=10.44; D=9.88	5.026	.002	Highly Sig.
Personal Development and Fulfillment	A=22.97; C=24.00 B=21.83; D=20.43	8.878	.000	Highly Sig.
Recreation	A=17.28; C=17.28 B=16.33; D=16.02	3.701	.012	Sig.
Overall	A=88.63; C=92.92 B=85.58; D=80.85	8.875	.000	Highly Sig.

A=COED, B=CBA, C=CAS, D=CCJ; Not Sig. if p-value is greater than 0.05; sig. and highly sig. if p-value is less than 0.05 and 0.01, respectively.

Table 4.2 presented the dimensions of QoL and their variations across program clusters. CAS had the highest overall mean QoL score at 92.92, while CCJ recorded the lowest at 80.85. ANOVA analysis confirmed significant differences with an F-value of 8.875 and a p-value of .000. These results indicated that program clusters influenced students' QoL, with CAS consistently scoring higher, suggesting factors such as academic demands, campus resources, and social support networks as possible influences. Moreover, the analysis of every domain also affirms substantial significant differences across program clusters.

Vitalia et al. (2019) supported these findings, emphasizing how academic programs affect interpersonal dynamics, noting psychology students' higher sensitivity, cooperation, and emotional openness, which likely foster mutual respect while attending to personal and others' needs. This aligns with CAS scoring highest in domains related to relational and personal development aspects of QoL. They further highlighted the proactive engagement with self-understanding and academic enrichment among psychology students, which highlight the program's role in fostering individual development and intellectual fulfillment. However, Wilzer et al. (2024) presented a contrasting view, suggesting psychology students might experience elevated stress and lower QoL due to course-specific pressures. Despite this, the overall findings reaffirmed significant program-specific differences in QoL levels across clusters, with CAS demonstrating the most favorable outcomes.

Table 5 *Correlation Analysis on the level of MHL and the QoL of the participants*

Dimensions of MHL to QoL	r	p	Conclusion
Disorder Recognition	.362	.000	Highly Sig.
Risk-Factor Knowledge	.125	.024	Sig.
Self -Treatment Knowledge	.070	.208	No Sig.
Available Professional Help Knowledge	.255	.000	Highly Sig.
Information Seeking Knowledge	.346	.000	Highly Sig.
Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion	.593	.000	Highly Sig.
Overall	.710	.000	Highly Sig.

Table 5 presented the association between different dimensions of MHL and overall QoL. Disorder Recognition showed a highly significant positive correlation with QoL ($r = .362$, $p = .000$), indicating that students who effectively identified mental health disorders tended to have a higher QoL. Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion also showed a highly significant positive correlation ($r = .593$, $p = .000$), suggesting that students with a strong understanding of mental health promotion experienced better QoL. Other dimensions, such as Risk-Factor Knowledge, Self-Treatment Knowledge, Available Professional Help Knowledge, and Information Seeking Knowledge, were also analyzed with varying degrees of association with QoL. The correlation between overall MHL and QoL was notably strong, with an r -value of 0.710 and a p -value of .000, which highlighted a substantial positive relationship between these two variables among college students. These findings imply a notable association between the level of MHL and QoL among college students. In simpler terms, variations in MHL levels are predictive of corresponding changes in overall QoL. As MHL levels increase or decrease, the overall well-being of students is affected in tandem, indicating the major contribution of MHL in shaping and predicting their overall QoL.

The findings are congruent with several research studies by Musa et al. (2022), Jafari et al. (2021), and Posai et al. (2021) which collectively emphasized the significant impact of MHL on the QoL across various populations. Musa et al. (2022) findings indicated that university students equipped with MHL exhibit notably higher QoL, suggesting the importance of mental health education and help-seeking behaviors. Similarly, Jafari et al. (2021) found a positive correlation between MHL and QoL among their general population, emphasizing the need for increased attention to MHL.

Also, Posai et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of MHL in promoting good mental health and improving QoL, particularly for stroke patients. They advocate for healthcare professionals, especially nurses and allied health professionals, to prioritize the assessment and enhancement of patients' MHL to ensure better QoL outcomes. Furthermore, Zarezadeh et al. (2020) stressed the significance of health literacy, which integrates MHL, in predicting QoL in society, emphasizing its function in promoting health behaviors and ultimately enhancing QoL. These findings collectively emphasized the importance of addressing MHL as a key factor in improving QoL across different populations.

Conclusions

Primarily, the level of Mental Health Literacy (MHL) of the participants, when assessed in terms of various subscales, is notably high. In the Disorder Recognition domain, participants demonstrated a substantial capacity to accurately recognize symptoms of various mental health disorders. The Risk-Factor Knowledge domain indicated that participants possessed a general awareness of the factors contributing to mental health issues, reflecting a good grasp of social determinants of mental health. In the Self-Treatment Knowledge domain, participants exhibited an understanding of effective self-treatment practices, which is crucial for managing their mental health independently. The Available Professional Help Knowledge domain revealed that

participants are well-informed about the resources available for mental health support, including therapeutic approaches and ethical considerations. Participants demonstrated confidence in the Information-Seeking Knowledge domain, indicating their ability to actively seek information and utilize diverse resources for mental health information. In the Knowledge Towards Positive Mental Health Promotion domain, participants showed favorable attitudes toward mental health promotion and a tendency to seek professional assistance, rejecting stigmatizing beliefs.

Moreover, the level of Quality of Life (QoL) of the participants, when assessed in terms of various subscales, is high. In the Physical and Material Well-Being domain, participants reported high levels of satisfaction, indicating a stable and comfortable lifestyle that meets their basic needs. The Relations with Other People domain showed significant satisfaction among participants with their interpersonal relations, reflecting strong and supportive social networks. Participants exhibited a high level of satisfaction in the Social, Community, and Civic Activities domain, indicating active participation in social, community, and civic pursuits. In the Personal Development and Fulfillment domain, participants reported high satisfaction levels, suggesting active engagement in learning, personal growth, and creative endeavors. The Recreation domain indicated that participants found pleasure in social interactions and various recreational pursuits, contributing to their overall well-being.

The analysis also revealed significant differences in MHL and QoL levels when grouped according to demographic profiles. Female participants exhibited higher MHL scores compared to males, indicating a gender disparity. Additionally, significant variations in MHL levels were observed across program clusters, with the College of Arts and Sciences (CAS) showing the highest MHL. Similarly, significant differences in QoL were noted, with females generally reporting higher QoL scores. The CAS also exhibited the highest QoL levels, which emphasized the influence of academic and social environments on students' well-being. Lastly, the study demonstrated a strong significant positive association between overall MHL and QoL. As MHL levels increase or decrease, overall QoL is affected in tandem which emphasizes the essential importance of MHL in shaping and predicting students' overall QoL. These findings suggest that improving MHL can lead to substantial benefits in students' QoL.

Recommendations

In connection with the implications revealed by the results and findings, the following recommendations are being advanced:

First, the Counseling and Testing Office should assess aspects requiring development in service provision, especially in assisting students with MHL, by identifying improvement areas and creating effective support programs to enhance students' QoL. Next, college students should be encouraged to develop their mental health knowledge to better manage their academic and personal lives and to utilize available mental health services.

For the institution, it is essential to establish programs addressing both academic and psychological well-being, including workshops, counseling, and curriculum

adjustments to prioritize students' MHL and QoL. The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) should use these findings to inform national policies and programs promoting MHL and QoL among students, ensuring adequate support for their holistic development. Lastly, future researchers should build on these findings to further explore MHL and QoL, using diverse methods and populations to deepen understanding of their associations. These recommendations aim to guide various stakeholders in enhancing Mental Health Literacy and the Quality of Life for college students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research study received approval from the institution's Research Internal Ethics Committee prior to survey administration, ensuring thorough ethical considerations were incorporated. Informed consent was obtained from all participants through a comprehensive consent form that outlined the study's purpose, procedures, and participants' rights, confirming their voluntary involvement and their ability to withdraw at any time without penalty. Respect for persons was upheld by recognizing each participant's autonomy and dignity, allowing them to decline participation whenever desired. The principles of beneficence and non-maleficence were prioritized to ensure participants' well-being and to prevent any harm. Additionally, confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained by anonymizing responses and securing personal information, ensuring participants' identities remained protected. Data was stored securely on a password-protected computer, with access limited to authorized personnel, and all personally identifiable information was omitted from any presentations or publications. By adhering to these ethical standards, the researchers ensured that the rights, privacy, and welfare of all participants were respected throughout the study.

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REFERENCES

Abesinghe, A., Katuwawela, K., Lakmali, K., Jayanetti, N., Munidasa, P., De Silva, B. S., & Marikar, F. (2023). Mental health literacy: A survey of the public's ability to recognize mental disorders and their knowledge about the effectiveness of helpful interventions to

- help the victims. *Journal of Evidence-Based Psychotherapies*, 23, 173-202.
<https://doi.org/10.24193/jebp.2023.2.16>
- Abrams, Z. (2022). Student mental health is in crisis. Campuses are rethinking their approach. *APA Monitor*. Retrieved from <https://www.apa.org/monitor/2022/10/mental-health-campus-care>
- Adu, P., Jurcik, T., & Grigoryev, D. (2023). Mental health literacy for social phobia in Ghana: Investigation of gender stereotypes and previous experience for recognition rates and prejudice. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 70(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/00207640231206055>
- Aloia, L. S. (2020). Parent–child relationship satisfaction: The influence of family communication orientations and relational maintenance behaviors. *The Family Journal*, 28(1), 83-89.
- Alqassim, A., Makeen, A., Ahmed, A., Alqarny, A., Alrabae, A., Aboalqasim, A., Ageel, A., Alnami, A., Hassani, M., Hakami, M., Mahfouz, M., & Alharbi, A. (2022). Exploring awareness, attitude, and practices toward mental illnesses: A cross-sectional survey among university students in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 11(8), 4568–4575. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc_2023_21
- Alvestad, T. M., & Johansen, S. M. (2020). An investigation of courage, emotion and well-being in relation to adventurous activities. *Munin.uit.no*.
<https://munin.uit.no/handle/10037/21131>
- Ameer, S., Malik, S., & Adil, A. (2022). Relationship of intrinsic and extrinsic aspirations with quality of life of university students: Mediating role of perceived academic stress. *Journal of Behavioral Sciences*, 32(2).
- Anjorin, O., & Wada, Y. H. (2022). Impact of traditional healers in the provision of mental health services in Nigeria. *Annals of Medicine & Surgery*, 82, Article 104755.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amsu.2022.104755>
- Argao, R. C. C., Reyes, M. E. S., & Delariarte, C. F. (2021). Mental health literacy & mental health of Filipino college students. *North American Journal of Psychology*, 23(3), 437.
- Arslan, S., & Karabey, S. (2023). High school students' and teachers' mental health literacy levels in Istanbul, Turkey: A comprehensive analysis. *The Journal of School Health*, 93(8), 698–706. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.13316>
- Baklola, M., Terra, M., Taha, A., Elnemr, M., Yaseen, M., Maher, A., & El-Gilany, A. H. (2024). Mental health literacy and help-seeking behaviour among Egyptian undergraduates: A cross-sectional national study. *BMC Psychiatry*, 24(1), 202.
- Barroso, R., & Dias, D. (2023). Creative environment in the classroom and students' satisfaction with school. *Revista Colombiana de Educación*, (88), 257-277.
- Batiancila, M. J. Q., Batuyong, M. J. V., Bautista, A. J. P., & Elnar, R. D. (2023). Validating the psychometric properties of mental health literacy scale among Filipino college students. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 49(2), 91–103.
<https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2023/v49i21122>
- Beasley, L., Kiser, R., & Hoffman, S. (2020). Mental health literacy, self-efficacy, and stigma among college students. *Social Work in Mental Health*, 18(6), 634-650.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/15332985.2020.1832643>
- Berg, M., Malmquist, A., Rozental, A., Topooco, N., & Andersson, G. (2020). Knowledge gain and usage of knowledge learned during internet-based CBT treatment for adolescent depression - A qualitative study. *BMC Psychiatry*, 20(1), 441.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-020-02833-4>
- Burckhardt, C. S., & Anderson, K. L. (2003). The Quality of Life Scale (QOLS): Reliability, validity, and utilization. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 1(60).
<https://doi.org/10.1186/1477-7525-1-60>

- Castellanos Silva, R., & Steins, G. (2023). Social media and body dissatisfaction in young adults: An experimental investigation of the effects of different image content and influencing constructs. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1037932.
- Cheah, W. L., Law, L. S., Teh, K. H., Kam, S. L., Voon, G. E. H., Lim, H. Y., & Shashi Kumar, N. S. (2021). Quality of life among undergraduate university students during COVID-19 movement control order in Sarawak. *Health Science Reports*, 4(3), e362.
- Chen C, Chen Y, Huang Q, Yan S, & Zhu J. (2022). Self-Care Ability of Patients with Severe Mental Disorders: Based on Community Patients Investigation in Beijing, China. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, 847098. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.847098>
- Cherry, K. (2023). Correlation studies in psychology research. Verywell Mind. <https://www.verywellmind.com/correlational-research>
- Chinene, B., Mpezeni, L., & Mudadi, L. (2023). Mental health literacy of undergraduate radiography students in Zimbabwe. *Journal of Medical Imaging and Radiation Sciences*, 54(4), 662–669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmir.2023.08.005>
- Cormier, E., Park, H., & Schluck, G. College students' eMental health literacy and risk of diagnosis with mental health disorders. *Healthcare*, 10, 2406. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare10122406>
- Dickinson, J., Griffiths, T. L., & Bredice, A. (2021). 'It's just another thing to think about': Encouraging students' engagement in extracurricular activities. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 45(6), 744-757.
- Dolipas, M. T. B. (2021). Perceptions on Politics and Political Participation of Benguet State University Students. *Mountain Journal of Science and Interdisciplinary Research (formerly Benguet State University Research Journal)*, 81(1), 66-83.
- Down, M., Picknoll, D., Piggott, B., Hoyne, G. F., & Bulsara, C. (2023). "I love being in the outdoors": A qualitative descriptive study of outdoor adventure education program components for adolescent wellbeing. *Journal of Adolescence*, 95(6), 1232–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jad.12197>
- El Khalil, R. (2023). Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS) validation studies: A scoping review. *Population Medicine*, 5(Supplement), A1323. <https://doi.org/10.18332/popmed/164053>
- Flaherty, L. (2022). The Effects of Stigma on Quality of Life and Psychological Outcomes in Participants with Varying Reports of Subjective Cognitive Decline. *Electronic Theses and Dissertations*. <https://doi.org/10.18297/etd/3993>
- Fleetwood, D. (2023, November 27). Quantitative Research: What It Is, Practices & Methods. *QuestionPro*. <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/quantitative-research/>
- Gharebaglou, M., Beyti, H., & Rezaei Zunuz, S. (2021). The Impact of the Sense of Home on the Quality of Life of Older Adults in Tabriz, Iran. *Journal of Aging and Environment*, 36(4), 410-432.
- Gopal, R., Singh, V., & Aggarwal, A. (2021). Impact of online classes on the satisfaction and performance of students during the pandemic period of COVID 19. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 6923-6947.
- Gorczyński, P., & Sims-Schouten, W. (2024). Evaluating mental health literacy amongst US college students: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of American College Health*, 72(3), 676–679. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2022.2063690>
- Höglund, B., & Hildingsson, I. (2023). Why and when choosing child-free life in Sweden? Reasons, influencing factors and personal and societal factors: Individual interviews during 2020–2021. *Sexual & Reproductive Healthcare*, 35, 100809.
- Ishikawa, H., Kato, M., & Kiuchi, T. (2021). Declines in health literacy and health-related quality of life during the COVID-19 pandemic: A longitudinal study of the Japanese general population. *BMC Public Health*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-021-12092-x>

- Jafari, A., Nejatian, M., Momeniyan, V., Barsalani, F. R., & Tehrani, H. (2021). Mental health literacy and quality of life in Iran: A cross-sectional study. *BMC Psychiatry*.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-021-03507-5>
- Jaradat, D., Ford-Gilboe, M., Berman, H., & Wong, C. (2022). Structural and construct validity of the Quality of Life Scale among Canadian women with histories of intimate partner violence. *Women's Health*, 18, 17455057221125574.
- Johnson, R. L., Nandan, M., Culp, B., & Thomas, D. (2023). College Students' Mental Health Help-Seeking Behaviors. *College Student Affairs Journal*, 41(1).
- Jonsson, P., Christiansen, F., & Brulin, E. (2023). The association between self-treatment and mental health among Swedish physicians. *Occupational medicine (Oxford, England)*, 73(5), 243–248. <https://doi.org/10.1093/occmed/kqad061>
- Korhonen, J., Axelin, A., Stein, D. J., Seedat, S., Mwape, L., Jansen, R., Groen, G., Grobler, G., Jörns-Presentati, A., Katajisto, J., Lahti, M., & MEGA Consortium/Research Team (2022). Mental health literacy among primary healthcare workers in South Africa and Zambia. *Brain and behavior*, 12(12), e2807. <https://doi.org/10.1002/brb3.2807>
- Koutra, K., Pantelaiou, V., & Mavroeides, G. (2024). Breaking Barriers: Unraveling the Connection between Mental Health Literacy, Attitudes towards Mental Illness, and Self-Stigma of Psychological Help-Seeking in University Students. *psychology international*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.3390/psycholint6020035>
- Lacsamana, B. (2022). YouTube, TikTok replace consultation: Students self-diagnose their mental health. *BusinessWorld Online*. Retrieved November 17, 2023, from <https://www.bworldonline.com/health/2022/05/04/446080/youtube-tiktok-replace-consultation-students-self-diagnose-their-mental-health/>
- Lee, J. E., Goh, M. L., & Yeo, S. F. (2023). Mental health awareness of secondary schools students: Mediating roles of knowledge on mental health, knowledge on professional help, and attitude towards mental health. *Heliyon*, 9(3).
- Lee, K.H., Xu, H., & Wu, B. (2020). Gender differences in quality of life among community-dwelling older adults in low- and middle-income countries: Results from the Study on global AGEing and adult health (SAGE). *BMC Public Health*, 20, 114.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-8212-0>
- Lee, S. (2023). Loneliness, volunteering, and quality of life in European older adults. *Activities, Adaptation & Aging*, 47(2), 250-261.
- Li, H., & Zhong, B. (2022). Quality of life among college students and its associated factors: A narrative review. *AME Medical Journal*, 7, 38. <https://doi.org/10.21037/amj-22-96>
- Lieberman, L. J., Haibach-Beach, P., Perreault, M., & Stribing, A. (2022). Outdoor recreation experiences in youth with visual impairments: A qualitative inquiry. *Journal of Adventure Education and Outdoor Learning*, 23(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/14729679.2021.1984965>
- Louzado, J. A., Lopes Cortes, M., Galvão Oliveira, M., Moraes Bezerra, V., Mistro, S., Souto de Medeiros, D., Arruda Soares, D., Oliveira Silva, K., Nicolaevna Kochergin, C., Honorato Dos Santos de Carvalho, V. C., Wildes Amorim, W., & Serrate Mengue, S. (2021). Gender differences in the quality of life of formal workers. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(11), 5951.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18115951>
- Mahmoodi, S. M. H., Ahmadzad-Asl, M., Eslami, M., Abdi, M., Hosseini Kahnamoui, Y., & Rasoulilian, M. (2022). Mental health literacy and mental health information-seeking behavior in Iranian university students. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13, 893534.
- Martinez, A. B., Co, M., Lau, J., & Brown, J. S. (2020). Filipino help-seeking for mental health problems and associated barriers and facilitators: A systematic review. *Social Psychiatry and Psychiatric Epidemiology*, 55, 1397-1413.

- Martínez-Royert, J. C., Peñate, M. P., & Pájaro-Martínez, M. C. (2022). Family functionality and life satisfaction in college students. Retrieved from <https://www.webology.org/abstract.php?id=3356#>
- Montagni, I., & González Caballero, J. L. (2022). Validation of the Mental Health Literacy Scale in French university students. *Behavioral Sciences*, 12(8), 259. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs12080259>
- Moss, R. A., Gorczyński, P., Sims-Schouten, W., Heard-Laureote, K., & Creaton, J. (2022). Mental health and wellbeing of postgraduate researchers: Exploring the relationship between mental health literacy, help-seeking behaviour, psychological distress, and wellbeing. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 41(4), 1168-1183. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07294360.2021.1906210>
- Mridha, M. (2020). The effect of age, gender and marital status on residential satisfaction. *Local Environment*, 25(8), 540–558. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2020.1801615>
- Musa, S. N. S., Hamzah, S. R., Badrudin, M., Amiludin, N., Zameram, Q., Kamaruzaman, M., Said, N., & Haniff, N. (2022). Association of social support and mental health literacy with quality of life among university students during the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v12-i7/14296>
- Nejatian, M., Tehrani, H., Momeniyan, V., et al. (2021). A modified version of the mental health literacy scale (MHLS) in Iranian people. *BMC Psychiatry*, 21, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-021-03050-3>
- Nelson, R. M., Tran, C., Reichenberg, R. E., & Vu, P. (2022). An evaluation of quality of life for former gifted program participants in Vietnam. *Gifted and Talented International*, 37(2), 97-108.
- Nguyen, T. Q.-C., Hoang-Minh, D., & Thi Kim-Anh, L. (2021). Recognition of anxiety disorder and depression and literacy of first-aid support: A cross-sectional study among undergraduate students in Ha Noi, Viet Nam 2018. *Health Psychology Open*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20551029211015116>
- O'Connor, M., & Casey, L. (2015). The Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS): A new scale-based measure of mental health literacy. *Psychiatry Research*, 229(1-2), 511-516.
- Orines, R., Dy, M., Huen, K., Maligaya, K., Pangan, J., Paulino, N., & Racimo, K. (2023). Stress and Avoidant Coping: Predictors of Quality of Life Among Filipino Graduating Students. *European Journal of Psychology and Educational Research*, 6(2), 77-83.
- Palimaru, A. I., McDonald, K., Garvey, R., D'Amico, E. J., & Tucker, J. S. (2023). The Association between Housing Stability and Perceived Quality of Life among Emerging Adults with a History of Homelessness. *Hindawi Health & Social Care in the Community*. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/2402610>
- Patterson, A. S. (2023). Biomedical and Spiritual Approaches to Mental Health in Tanzania: How Power and the Struggle for Public Authority Shaped Care. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 1-27.
- Ponzini, Gabriella & Snider, Mira & Evey, Kelsey & Steinman, Shari. (2021). Women's Knowledge of Postpartum Anxiety Disorders, Depression, and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. *Journal of Nervous & Mental Disease*. Publish Ahead of Print. 10.1097/NMD.0000000000001315.
- Posai, V., Boonchoo, R., Watradul, D., Makkabphalanon, K., & Thangkratok, P. (2021). Mental health literacy and quality of life among patients with stroke. *Chiang Mai Medical Journal*, 60(1), 63-74.
- Prifti, R. (2022). Self-efficacy and student satisfaction in the context of blended learning courses. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 37(2), 111-125.

- Publico, M. R. (2020). Assessing the Mental Health Literacy of Secondary School Educators. *International Journal of Childhood Education*, 1(1), 24–31. <https://doi.org/10.33422/ijce.v1i1.11>
- Puhakka, R. (2021). University students' participation in outdoor recreation and the perceived well-being effects of nature. *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism*, 36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jort.2021.100425>
- Puspitasari, I. M., Garnisa, I. T., Sinuraya, R. K., & Witriani, W. (2020). Perceptions, Knowledge, and Attitude Toward Mental Health Disorders and Their Treatment Among Students in an Indonesian University. *Psychology research and behavior management*, 13, 845–854. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S274337>
- Ran, M., Peng, L., Liu, Q., Pender, M., He, F., & Wang, H. (2018). The association between quality of life (QOL) and health literacy among junior middle school students: a cross-sectional study. *BMC public health*, 18(1), 1183. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-6082-5>
- Renwick, L., Pedley, R., Johnson, I., et al. (2022). Mental health literacy in children and adolescents in low- and middle-income countries: A mixed studies systematic review and narrative synthesis. *European Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00787-022-01997-6>
- Salsabilla, F. P. (2023). Literature Review: Confidentiality Issues Between Guidance and Counselling Teachers and Colleagues. *Psikoeduko: Jurnal Psikologi Edukasi dan Konseling*, 3(2), 1-16.
- Serrano, J. O., & Reyes, M. E. S. (2022). Bending not breaking: coping among Filipino University students experiencing psychological distress during the Global Health Crisis. Springer Link. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03823-3>
- Staiger, T., Stiawa, M., Mueller-Stierlin, A. S., Kilian, R., Beschoner, P., Gündel, H., Becker, T., Fräsch, K., Panzirsch, M., Schmauß, M., & Krumm, S. (2020). Masculinity and Help-Seeking Among Men With Depression: A Qualitative Study. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 11. [10.3389/fpsy.2020.59903](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.59903)
- Stunden C, Zasada J, VanHeerwaarden N, Hollenberg E, Abi-Jaoudé A, Chaim G, Cleverley K, Henderson J, Johnson A, Levinson A, Lo B, Robb J, Shi J, Voineskos A, Wiljer D.(2020). Help-Seeking Behaviors of Transition-Aged Youth for Mental Health Concerns: Qualitative Study. *J Med Internet Res* 2020;22(10). <https://doi.org/10.2196/18514>
- Sulaiman, N., Nurulhudha, M. J., Adznam, S. N., Adznam, A., Azahari, S., & Zainal Badari, S. (2020). Financial problems associated with food insecurity among public university students in Peninsular Malaysia. *Malaysian Journal of Nutrition*, 26, 411-423. DOI: [10.31246/mjn-2020-0032](https://doi.org/10.31246/mjn-2020-0032)
- Sullivan, P., Murphy, J., & Blacker, M. (2019). The level of mental health literacy among athletic staff in intercollegiate sport. *Journal of Clinical Sport Psychology*, 13(3), 440-450.
- Tohme, P., Abi Fadel, N., Yaktine, N., & Abi-Habib, R. (2024). Predictors of Mental Health Literacy in a Sample of Health Care Major Students: Pilot Evaluation Study. *JMIR Formative Research*, 8(1), e43770.
- Vitalia, I., Răban-Motounu, N., Stan, M., Ciucurel, M. M., & Bădulescu, A. (2019). Personal development in first-year psychology students. In E. Soare & C. Langa (Eds.), *Education facing contemporary world issues*, vol. 67. *European Proceedings of Social and Behavioural Sciences* (pp. 2041-2048). Future Academy. <https://doi.org/10.15405/epsbs.2019.08.03.252>
- White, M., & Casey, L. (2017). Helping older adults to help themselves: The role of mental health literacy in family members. *Aging & Mental Health*, 21(11), 1129–1137.

- Wilzer, E., Zeisel, A., Roessner, V., & Ring, M. (2024). Association between anxiety, depression and quality of life in male and female German students during the COVID-19 pandemic. *BMC psychiatry*, 24(1), 212.
- Wu, Y., Yu, W., Wu, X., Wan, H., Wang, Y., & Lu, G. (2020). Psychological resilience and positive coping styles among Chinese undergraduate students: A cross-sectional study. *BMC psychology*, 8(1), 79. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-020-00444-y>
- Xi, J., Lee, M. T., Carter, J. R., & Delgado, D. (2022). Gender Differences in Purpose in Life: The Mediation Effect of Altruism. *Journal of Humanistic Psychology*, 62(3), 352-376. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022167818777658>
- Yarmohammadi, S., Ghaffari, M., Yarmohammadi, H., Hosseini Koukamari, P., & Ramezankhani, A. (2020). Relationship between Quality of Life and Body Image Perception in Iranian Medical Students: Structural Equation Modeling. *International journal of preventive medicine*, 11, 159. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijpvm.IJPVM_203_19
- Zarezadeh, Y., Eskandari, N., Moradi, M., & Abdi, N. (2020). The relationship between health literacy and quality of life of employees in campus of Kurdistan University of Medical Sciences. *Journal of Health Literacy*, 4(4), 38-45. <http://doi.org/10.22038/jhl.2020.44567.1088>
- Zuo, Z., Li, S., Liu, S., & Wang, Q. (2022). Life satisfaction and parental support among secondary school students in Urumqi: The mediation of physical activity. *PeerJ*, 10, e14122. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.14122>